

New Hampshire Declaration of Faith

also known as "New Hampshire Confession of Faith", "New Hampshire Statement of Faith"

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Entry tags: Creed, Religious Group, Text, Baptists

The New Hampshire Declaration of Faith was the statement of faith adopted by the Baptist State Convention of New Hampshire on January 15, 1833. It was composed by a committee including I. Pearson, B. Stow, and J. Newton Brown. (Hurlin, et. al, 1902,56) The first edition included sixteen articles summarizing key components of Christian Doctrine. An expanded edition published in J. Newton Brown's Church Manual included two additional articles. Brown's Church Manual also included a church covenant. The first edition and Brown's edition included references to the Bible to explain or defend the articles. Sometimes, the Scripture references were omitted or abridged. A significant number of Baptist churches adopted the New Hampshire Declaration as a summary statement of Baptist beliefs. Many different kinds of Baptists adopted this document as well, or modified it to fit local or institutional needs. Southwestern Baptist Theological Seminary's adoption of the New Hampshire Declaration with amendment is one example of the malleability of the Declaration. It provided a base text for the first edition of the Southern Baptist "Baptist Faith and Message" and the Baptist Bible Union's "Articles of Faith, 1923."

Date Range: 1833 CE - 2023 CE

Region: New Hampshire

Region tags: New Hampshire, United States

US State of New Hampshire

Status of Readership:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.reformedreader.org/ccf/1833newh.htm>

– Source 1 Description: An online edition of the New Hampshire Declaration of Faith (Brown's edition.)

– Source 2 URL: <http://hdl.handle.net/2263/67778>.

– Source 2 Description: E. Peter Frank Lumpkins "The Decline of Confessional Calvinism among Baptist Associations in the Southern States during the Nineteenth Century" argues that the New Hampshire Declaration of Faith and its reception represents a move away from Calvinist theology among Baptists in the United States.

– Source 3 URL: https://swbtsv7.s3.amazonaws.com/media/Theology_Journal/51.2/51.2_Commentary.pdf.

– Source 3 Description: B. H. Carroll, first President of Southwestern Baptist Theological Seminary, provides an exposition of the New Hampshire Declaration of Faith.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/baptistconfessi00mcglgoog/page/n314/mode/2up?>
- Source 1 Description: William Joseph McGlothlin's anthology of Baptist confessions including the New Hampshire Declaration of Faith and his discription.
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/baptistconfessio0000lump/page/360/mode/2up>
- Source 2 Description: William Latane Lumpkin's anthology of Baptist confessions including the New Hampshire Declaration of Faith and his discription..

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Printed with moveable type

Number of sheets

- Bound

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Paper

Specify type of paper

- Specify: common wood based paper.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Corrections

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Corrections

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

- No

Is the location where the text is stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Notes: Anyone who has an interest in the Baptists or would like to become a Baptist.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing or missionary work part of the historical culture of the community referenced in the text?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?
– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?
– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?
– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: Sometimes the companion church covenant is used in ritual practice, but ritual recitation of the New Hampshire Statement of Faith is rare.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

- ↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?
 - No

- ↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?
 - No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

- ↳ Cultural with religious implications?
 - Yes

- ↳ Behavioral literature?
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Baptist Confessions of Faith

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Bibliography

Notes: Most editions include scriptural proof texts for each article. Some editions abridge or remove this list.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?
 - No

- ↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Other [specify]: adoption by a group of Baptists

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– No

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– I don't know

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or

spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Notes: There is a distinction between the intermediate state and after the final judgement.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

Notes: Christ will "descend from Heaven" so at least in the intermediate state it is described as above.

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarh (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
 - Yes

- ↳ Other features of the supreme high god
 - Specify: True, living, infinite intelligent, the Maker and supreme Ruler of heaven and earth; inexpressibly glorious in holiness, and worthy of all possible honor, confidence and love

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
 - Yes
 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
 - No

 - ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
 - No

 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
 - Yes

 - ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
 - Yes

 - ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
 - Yes

 - ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
 - Yes

 - ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
 - Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: The positive emotions like tenderest sympathies and being compassionate, are analogical. Divine Impassibility is at least part of academic theology affirmed by some baptists who use this statement.

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

Notes: The negative parallel clauses to the positive emotions are not emotion terms.

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: the Maker and supreme Ruler of heaven and earth; inexpressibly glorious in holiness, and worthy of all possible honor, confidence and love; that in the unity of the Godhead there are three persons, the Father, the Son, and the Holy Ghost; equal in every divine perfection and executing distinct but harmonious offices in the great work of redemption

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– I don't know

Notes: Article 6 On the Freeness of Salvation implies the category of general revelation with the phrase "voluntary rejection of the Gospel." It does not explicitly discuss that category of Christian revelation.

↳ In dreams

– I don't know

Notes: Article 1 Of the Scriptures discusses the composition of the Bible as divinely inspired and God as author, but it does not explain how both are true. There are dream narratives in the Bible. Any other "human conduct, creeds and opinions" are to be judged by the Bible.

↳ In trance possession

– I don't know

Notes: Article 1 Of the Scriptures discusses the composition of the Bible as divinely inspired and God as author, but it does not explain how both are true. There is at least one trance narrative in the Bible. Any other "human conduct, creeds and opinions" are to be judged by the Bible.

↳ Through divination practices

– I don't know

Notes: Article 1 Of the Scriptures discusses the composition of the Bible as divinely inspired and God as author, but it does not explain how both are true. There are condemnations of divination in the Bible, as well as rituals that are similar to divination. Any other "human conduct, creeds and opinions" are to be judged by the Bible.

↳ Only through religious specialists

– Yes

Notes: There is a distinction between the "men divinely inspired" in Of The Scriptures and "exercising the gifts, rights, and privileges invested in them by his word," and the "scriptural officers" in Of a Gospel Church.

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is the normative means of communication from God throughout the confession.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– No

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is the only both human-divine being. The Son of God "freely took upon him our nature."

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– Yes

Notes: Jesus is the only both human-divine being. The Son of God "freely took upon him our nature."

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: Jesus is the Mediator in Of the Harmony of Law and Gospel.

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: humans.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not say

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– I don't know

Notes: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: The document does not discuss particular things that God knows and judges in the final judgement.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: It is based on trust in God, and active imitation of his free mercy.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– I don't know

- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?
 - No
- ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?
 - No
- ↳ Other form of punishment
 - Specify: Separation from God.
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of bad luck?
 - No
 - ↳ Political failure?
 - No
 - ↳ Defeat in battle?
 - No
 - ↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
 - No
 - ↳ Disaster on journeys?
 - No
 - ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
 - No

- ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
 - No
- ↳ Sickness or illness?
 - No
- ↳ Impaired reproduction?
 - No
- ↳ Bad luck visited on descendants?
 - No
- ↳ Other?
 - Specify: Temporal punishments for sin are not specified.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– I don't know

Notes: The final judgment is based "on principles of righteousness." in OF the World to Come. However Of the Righteous and Wicked states "that such only as through faith are justified in the name of the Lord Jesus, and sanctified by the Spirit of our God, are [they] truly righteous in his esteem." Ritual-devotional adherence would be co-resulting from the establishment of righteousness.

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– I don't know

Notes: The final judgment is based "on principles of righteousness." in *Of the World to Come*. However *Of the Righteous and Wicked* states "that such only as through faith are justified in the name of the Lord Jesus, and sanctified by the Spirit of our God, are [they] truly righteous in his esteem." Group norm enforcement would be co-resulting from the establishment of righteousness.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– Yes

Notes: Baptists would reject the terms reincarnation and superior life form. They would prefer "Resurrection to a new life." The new life is a restoration to holiness, the happy state, and the physical consequences of the fall discussed in *Of the Fall of Man*.

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– Yes

Notes: Baptists would reject the term reincarnation. Resurrection will be dwelling in heaven with endless joy. The impact on creation of the fall of man will be restored.

- ↳ Other?
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
 - Yes

- ↳ Highly emphasized?
 - No

- ↳ Consists of good luck?
 - No

- ↳ Consists of political success or power?
 - No

- ↳ Consists of success in battle?
 - No

- ↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
 - Yes

- ↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
 - No

- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
 - No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

↳ Other?

–Specify: Obedience of civil government yields good order of civil society and is a divine blessing.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

↳ Other purpose

–Specify: Christ will descend from heaven, and raise the dead from the grave to final retribution; that a solemn separation will then take place; that the wicked will be adjudged to endless punishment, and the righteous to endless joy.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– Yes

- ↳ At specified time in future
 - No
- ↳ At unspecified time in near future
 - No
- ↳ At unspecified time in distant future
 - Yes
- ↳ At some other time [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - Yes
 - Notes: Christ will judge all.
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - I don't know
 - Notes: The means of grace are meant for sanctification and "preparation for the rest that remaineth for the people of God." How the religious system of those on earth interacts with the intermediate state or after the final judgment is not discussed.
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: Christ's judgment will fix forever the final state of men in heaven or hell, on principles of righteousness.

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive

– Yes

↳ A subset of the religion in-group members will survive

– Yes

↳ All members of the sample region will survive

– Yes

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton

– Yes

↳ Other survival condition [specify]

– Specify: Consious existence after the final judgment includes both the in-group and the out-group.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Weakly present

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entitites

– No

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– No

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– Yes

Notes: Jesus, the only human-divine being, is the basis for Christian Sabbath and the understanding of relations to civil government.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: Of the Freeness of Salvation states "We believe that the blessings of salvation are made free to all by the gospel; that it is the immediate duty of all to accept them by a cordial penitent, and obedient faith." Of Grace in Regeneration and Of Civil Government state that this adherence though for all people, should not be compelled by force.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

Notes: Perseverance is a gift of God.

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: Baptism is specifically a beautiful emblem.

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

↳ By the community?

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals?

– No

↳ Is the maintenance of the place regulated by the text?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Faith Elect

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Faith Elect

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Notes: It does not condemn non-religious education either.

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Mullins, Edgar Young. Baptist Beliefs. Louisville: Baptist World, 1919.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, McClothlin, William J., ed.. "The New Hampshire Confession". In Baptist Confessions of Faith, 299–307. Philadelphia: American Baptist Publication Society, 1911.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Barnes, William Wright. "The New Hampshire Confession of Faith, Its Origins, and Use". *Review & Expositor* 39, no. 1 (January 1942): 3–8. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003463734203900101>.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, J. Newton, Brown. Baptist Church Manual. Philadelphia: American Baptist Publication Society, 1853.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Lumpkin, William L.. "Baptist Confessions of Faith". In *Baptist Advance: The Achievements of Baptists of North America for a Century and a Half*, edited by Robert Andrew Baker, 8–15. Nashville: Broadman, 1964.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Lumpkin, William L., and Bill J. Leonard, eds.. "The New Hampshire Confession, 1833". In *Baptist Confessions of Faith*, 2nd revised ed... Philadelphia: Judson Press, 2011.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Lumpkins, E. Peter Frank. "The New Hampshire Declaration of Faith: Reevaluating Its Impact on Baptists in the South During the Nineteenth Century". *Journal of Baptist Theology and Ministry* 15, no. 2 (September 2018): 30–47. https://www.nobts.edu/baptist-center-theology/journals/journals/JBTM_15-2_Fall_2018.pdf.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Lumpkins, E. Peter Frank. "The Decline of Confessional Calvinism Among Baptist Associations in the Southern States During the Nineteenth Century". PhD Thesis, University of Pretoria, 2018. <http://hdl.handle.net/2263/67778>.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, MacDonald, Charles Riley. "The New Hampshire Declaration of Faith". Ph.D. Dissertation, Northern Baptist Theological Seminary, 1939.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Carroll, Benajah Harvey. "Foundations of Our Faith". Edited by Calvin Goodspeed. *Southwestern Journal of Theology* 51, no. 2 (2009): 134–256. https://swbtsv7.s3.amazonaws.com/media/Theology_Journal/51.2/51.2_Commentary.pdf.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Wolever, Terry. "Another Look at the Origins of the New Hampshire Baptist Confession of 1833". In *An Anthology of Early Baptists in New Hampshire*, 528–42. Springfield, MO: Particular Baptist Press, 2001.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Estep, William Roscoe. "Baptists and Authority: The Bible, Confessions, and Conscience in the Development of Baptist Identity." *Review & Expositor* 84, no. 4 (December 1987): 599–615. <https://doi.org/10.1177/003463738708400403>.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Englerth, Gilbert R.. "American Baptists: A Confessional People?". *American Baptist Quarterly* 4, no. 2 (June 1958): 131–45.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Schaff, Phillip, and David S. Schaff, eds.. "The New Hampshire Confession, A.D. 1833". In *Creeds of Christendom*, 3:742–48. New York: Harper and Row, 1931.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Pelikan, Jaroslav, and Valerie Hotchkiss, eds.. "New Hampshire Baptist Convention, Declaration of Faith, (the New Hampshire Confession), 1833/1853". In *Creeds & Confessions of Faith in the Christian Tradition*, 3:242–49. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2003.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, McCormick, Jonathan A.. "The Genealogy of a Confessional Tradition: A Source Critical Analysis of the 1925 Baptist Faith and Message". PhD Dissertation, Gateway Seminary, 2019.

Reference: New Hampshire Declaration of Faith, Hurlin, William, O.C. Sargent, and W.W. Wakeman. "The New Hampshire Declaration of Faith". In *The Baptists of New Hampshire*, 50–57. Manchester, NH: John B. Clarke, 1902. <https://books.google.com/books?id=kVtDAAAAYAAJ&pg=PA50#v=onepage&q&f=false>.